

Fig. S1. Percentage of missing daily values for each climate variable over the 2000-2021 period. Data to impute (in the red rectangle) were measured at Yasuní Forest Dynamic Plot (YFDP). Imputation robustness was improved by including weather station data (2010 to 2022; blue rectangle) for maximum, minimum and average temperature (tempmax, tempmin, temp) and average relative humidity (humidity), obtained from a station located ~115km east of the YFDP (Visualcrossing data: <https://www.visualcrossing.com>) (Fig. S5). IRRA = irradiance; RAIN = rainfall; TMIN/TMAX = minimum/maximum temperature; RHAVE = average relative humidity.

Fig. S2. Percentage of missing values for each day of the month and each climate variable, calculated over the whole study period (2000-2021). TMIN/TAVE/TMAX = minimum/average/maximum temperature; RHMIN/RHAVE = minimum/average relative humidity. The dotted horizontal line corresponds to the percentage of missing values (45.5%) for the Nuevo Rocafuerte weather station (see Fig. S5).

Fig. S3. Percentage of days with 0 to 11 missing values across climate variables, calculated over the 2000-2021 period.

Fig. S5. Map showing the location of the Yasuní Forest Dynamic Plot (YFDP) and the Nuevo Rocafuerte weather station from which we obtained daily data for four climate variables (see Fig. S1).

Fig. S7. Post-Hoc analysis evaluating the reliability of the imputations of the missing climate data obtained with the BHPMF procedure, through the average RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) value plotted against the percentage of imputed data having a higher standard deviation from one iteration of gap filling ("fold") to the next (see Schrodtr et al. 2015 for details). The graph shows that with increasing uncertainty (RMSE), the imputation precision (Std) decreases. The more linear the relationship is, the more stable the model is, and thus the more accurate the imputation (F. Schrodtr, pers. communication). All standard deviation values of imputed data were < 0.976 (not shown).

Fig. S8. Post-Hoc analyses evaluating the reliability of the imputations of the missing climate data obtained with the BHPMF procedure. **(a)** Comparison of the correlation values among climate variables before and after imputation, showing a strong consistency (r-Pearson = 0.992). **(b)** Same as in (a) but showing correlations obtained with each climate variable. Filled black symbols emphasize the seven pairwise correlation values for each climate variable. All correlation values were > 0.994 .

Fig. S9. Observed (blue) and imputed (black) mean monthly values of each climate variable across the 2000-2021 study period. The red curve shows the inter-annual trend obtained from Seasonal-Trend by LOESS (STL) decomposition of imputed climate values. IRRA/RAIN/TMIN/TMAX/RHAVE = irradiance / rainfall / minimum temperature / maximum temperature / average relative humidity at the Yasuní Forest Dynamic Plot.

Fig. S10. Results of the regression models examining the effects (total, direct, flower-mediated) of the **average Relative Humidity (RH_{AVE})** on seed production (SP). See legend of Fig. 2 and Fig. 4 for details on the description of the figure.

Significant **positive** / **negative** slope coefficient ($P \leq 0.05$)

Slope of the lowest total effect = -0.74 ($P < 0.001$; MSR test; Mid-October to Mid-July)

Slope of the lowest direct effect = -0.52 ($P < 0.001$; MSR test; Mid-October to Mid-July)

Lowest/highest flower-mediated effect → Not significant

Fig. S11. Results of the regression models examining the effects (total, direct, flower-mediated) of **daytime Vapor Pressure Deficit (VPD_{DAY})** on seed production. See legend of Fig. 4 for details on the description of the figure.

Significant **positive** / **negative** slope coefficient ($P \leq 0.05$)

Slope of the highest total effect = 0.62 ($P < 0.001$; MSR test; September to July)

Slope of the highest direct effect = 0.45 ($P < 0.001$; MSR test; September to July)

Lowest/highest flower-mediated effect → Not significant

Fig. S12. (a) R^2 value (Y axis) quantifying the total effect (at the annual level), on seed production, of each climate variable in the “best” OLS model, *i.e.* the model producing the strongest overall slope coefficient (see Figure 2 for a more detailed explanation). VPD1 = average VPD (Vapor Pressure Deficit); VPD2 = daytime VPD. **(b)** Comparison of the highest absolute slope coefficient value obtained among climate predictors.

Fig. S13. Values and regression line of the seed production plotted against average relative humidity (RH_{ave}; left graph) and against the average vapor pressure deficit (VPD_{ave}; right graph), during the whole study period (black circles and full black line) and during the period where direct measurements were made for RH_{ave} (2008-2017; blue dots and blue dotted line). Values indicate the Pearson correlation of the relationship for each period.

Fig. S14. Model checking from ARIMA imputation of missing seed production data. Top panel: residuals of the ARIMA model across time (in months). The absence of residuals for imputed values (right end of the graph) is expected because residuals reflect deviations between actual observations and model predictions, and no observations exist for the missing points that were imputed. Bottom left: autocorrelation function (ACF) of the residuals: most autocorrelation values fell within the 95% confidence intervals (blue dashed lines). Significant spikes outside this range indicate that some residuals were not white noise. Manual adjustment of ARIMA model parameters did not help reducing the noise. Bottom right: residuals show approximate normal distribution, suggesting that the model fits the data moderately well. Thus, residuals mostly represent random noise left after accounting for temporal patterns (trends, seasonality, autocorrelation) in the seed production data.

Fig. S15. Observed and imputed (blue-shaded areas) seed production (z-score transformed values) across the study period. Imputed values were calculated using automatic ARIMA model fitting.

Fig. S16a,b. Wavelet coherence scores (colour gradient) between seed production and irradiance (a) and rainfall (b), across time (x-axis) and periodic domains (y-axis). The shaded transparent area above the arch represents regions in the wavelet coherence plot where results are less trustworthy due to edge effects. Below the arch, regions delimited by white lines and containing arrows represent areas where the coherence between the two time series is significant ($p \leq 0.05$; 1000 Monte Carlo simulations).

(a) Irradiance

(b) Rainfall

Fig. S16c,d. Wavelet coherence scores (colour gradient) between seed production and minimum temperature (T_{MIN} ; panel c) and maximum temperature (T_{MAX} ; panel d), across time (x-axis) and periodic domains (y-axis). The shaded transparent area above the arch represents regions in the wavelet coherence plot where results are less trustworthy due to edge effects. Below the arch, regions delimited by white lines and containing arrows represent areas where the coherence between the two time series is significant ($p \leq 0.05$; 1000 Monte Carlo simulations).

Fig. S16e. Wavelet coherence scores (colour gradient) between seed production and average vapor pressure deficit (VPD_{AVE}), across time (x-axis) and periodic domains (y-axis). The shaded transparent area above the arch represents regions in the wavelet coherence plot where results are less trustworthy due to edge effects. Below the arch, regions delimited by white lines and containing arrows represent areas where the coherence between the two time series is significant ($p \leq 0.05$; 1000 Monte Carlo simulations).

